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Key words: health, occupational health care, economic training profile, prevention, formation and preservation of health of specialists of the economic sphere.

Ключові слова: здоров'я, професійне здоров'я, економічний профіль підготовки, профілактика, формування та збереження професійного здоров'я фахівців економічної сфери

Ключевые слова: здоровье, профессиональное здоровье, экономический профиль подготовки, профилактика, становление и развитие профессионального здоровья специалистов экономической сферы

Abstract. Psychological bases of occupational health of specialists of economic sphere. Shevchenko O.A., Burlakova I.A., Sheviakov O.V., Agarkov O.A., Shramko I.A. A theoretical and methodological approach to the study of the process of professional health of specialists in the economic sphere was developed, which allowed to distinguish professionally important qualities of a specialist influencing his professional health, as well as to predict their transformation in changing social conditions. The peculiarities of the dynamics of the process of occupational health of specialists in the economic sphere (the stage of "primary formation" and undefined attitude to the profession; "personal-activity" stage - realization of social status at the level of the professional community; "professional-ethical" stage - values-based attitude to the profession) are revealed. Types of values-based attitude relation (neutral; pragmatic-realistic; values-based) to professional activity and peculiarities of their manifestations in specialists of economic sphere having different experience of such activity are determined. It is shown that the dynamics of professional becoming of specialists in the economic sphere is associated with the activation of changes in the internal and external environment of the subject of activity. The conceptual model of formation and preservation of professional health of specialists of the economic sphere is offered, implemented as a theoretical and methodological strategy of the systemic and holistic process in the direction of ensuring its effectiveness, presented in the form of an image of a healthy person, responsibly managing his own health and realizing himself in society, and an image of a specialist who independently sets the goals of formation and preservation of professional health, chooses the best ways and means and achievements. The developed model provides a qualitatively new level of personal, physical, professional and social readiness of the person for self-realization in the professional economic sphere of activity and successful integration into society.

Реферат. Психологічні основи професійного здоров'я фахівців економічної сфери. Шевченко О.А., Бурлакова І.А., Шевяков О.В., Агарков О.А., Шрамко І.А. Розроблено теоретико-методологічний підхід до дослідження професійного здоров'я фахівців економічної сфери, який дозволив виділити професійно важливі якості фахівця, що впливають на його професійне здоров'я, а також прогнозувати їх трансформацію при зміні соціальних умов. Виявлено особливості динаміки формування професійного здоров'я фахівців економічної сфери (етап первинного становлення і невизначеного ставлення до професії; особистісно-діяльнісний етап - реалізація соціального статусу на рівні професійного співтовариства; професійно-етичний етап - ціннісне ставлення до професії). Визначено типи ціннісного ставлення (нейтральний; прагматично-реалістичний; ціннісний) до професійної діяльності та особливості їх проявів у фахівців економічної сфери, що мають різний досвід такої діяльності. Показано, що динаміка професійного становлення фахівців економічної сфери пов'язана з активізацією змін внутрішнього і зовнішнього середовища суб'єкта діяльності. Запропоновано концептуальну модель формування та збереження професійного здоров'я фахівців економічної сфери, що реалізується як теоретико-методологічна стратегія системного і цілісного процесу в напрямку забезпечення його результативності, представлена у вигляді образу здорової особистості, відповідально керуючої власним здоров'ям і такої б, що реалізує себе в соціумі, та образу фахівця, який самостійно ставить мету формування і збереження професійного здоров'я, обирає оптимальні способи і засоби її досягнення. Розроблена модель забезпечує якісно новий рівень особистісної, фізичної, професійної та соціальної готовності особистості до самореалізації в професійній економічній сфері діяльності й успішної інтеграції в соціум.

The changes taking place in Ukraine require from a modern specialist of independence and responsibility – actions that characterize the value attitude to professional activity and one's own professional and personal development [7].

The self-reflection of a specialist reflects socio-cultural contradictions, trends of globalization and local conservatism, contradictory aspects of the interaction of cultures [2].

There is a loss of established notions of professional activity, by which a specialist defines himself and his place in society, that is, there is a crisis of professional formation at the level of self-consciousness, both individually and within generations. The sharp social changes, as well as the development of the system of interaction of cultural traditions, the intensification of migration processes have led to increased participation of the subject of activity in various real and virtual professional groups [9].

In these conditions, the integrity and formation of the psychological structure of occupational health of the individual becomes of great importance [3, 4].

The issue of health and occupational health has been the subject of research of many scholars, leading to many approaches to interpreting the phenomenon. The problems of preservation of human health in modern conditions and peculiarities of its personal and professional becoming, the specificity of life and professional development of the individual within the ontogenetic study of problems of life self-realization, its professional self-determination are distinguished. As a component of life development, the motivational and adaptive content of professional activity, the strategy of forming a healthy lifestyle, medical-pedagogical and psychological-pedagogical problems of forming a healthy lifestyle in young people, in particular students, are explored [5, 8].

At the same time, existing approaches to the study of the phenomenon of occupational health do not allow to analyze its structure as a holistic and comprehensively organized psychological education; to operationalize the hierarchical model of professional workers in the field of economy [6, 10].

Thus, at present there are unresolved problems in the field of professional workers, in particular the economic sphere of activity, and the unwillingness to cover the socio-psychological basis of the processes of its formation and preservation under the influence of global transformations of modern society and state development [11, 1].

The purpose is to determine the psychological factors of occupational health of specialists in the economic sphere for its formation and strengthening.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH

During the research phase, 630 specialists from the economic sphere (bank employees, financial analysts, business economists, heads of investment projects and programs, managers) with different professional experience (average age – 31.5 years) were recruited. Professional group of work with internal clients (administrators, assistants, managers) consisted of 240 people: 130 men and 110 women; professional staff working with external clients (sales managers, customer service managers, consultants) – 220 people: 124 men and 96 women; and in the professional group of executives (at various levels – from the head of the department to the general manager of medium business) – 170 participants: 92 men and 78 women.

Research methods:

Theoretical: analysis of scientific sources, synthesis, modeling, systemic, structural and functional methods used to determine the directions and conceptual bases of research of social and

psychological bases of professional health of specialists in the economic sphere;

Empirical: observation, conversation, peer review method, psychodiagnostic methods used to: study the professional health of professionals, its structure and its main components; determining the specificity of their occupational health and the nature of their relationship in the personality structure of the specialist; diagnostics (individual and group, complex, operative, in-depth), aimed at identifying the features of cognitive, emotional-volitional, personal spheres, and studying the level of motivation to maintain occupational health, emotional and vital intelligence, sociometric indices, the level of development of communicative indexes conflict, stress resistance, prognosis for occupational longevity and occupational disease, as well as occupational risks that reduce labor productivity and quality of life economic experts;

Methods of mathematical processing of data with their subsequent qualitative interpretation and meaningful generalization. Statistical data processing and graphical presentation of the survey results were performed using the SPSS statistical software package (version 16.0).

The conceptual model includes determining the level of occupational health of each specialist with appropriate conclusions and recommendations; preparation of a SWOT health analysis; development of programs for the prevention and prevention of chronic fatigue syndrome, emotional burnout syndrome and occupational deformity for managers and specialists in the economic sphere; consulting on individual health programs, as well as development and implementation of corporate motivational mini-projects (Table).

Scheme for determining occupational health of specialists of economic sphere

Factors	Essence	Personality Position
Emotional	Various emotional stressors affecting occupational health	The ability of a person to withstand stress, to express own emotions and to manage them, to adequately assess the emotions of others, which characterizes emotional stability
Cognitive	Knowledge about occupational health, about main factors that enhance and damage health, about its role in life	The ability of a person to make adequate decisions, to highlight the main thing, to find the information that is missing, the ability to think, stability and concentration of attention, critical thinking, professional memory, professional observation, speed of decision making, their volume and correctness, ability to think quickly and positively
Behavioral	Choosing a specific strategy for dealing with a stressful situation	Ability to quickly adapt to the requirements of the situation by mastering, mitigating or weakening these requirements

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is determined that managers are more focused on the past and present, and those who work with internal clients – on the future ($p \leq 0.01$). We believe this can be explained by: in most cases, leaders have a wealth of life experience, a successful career that they are proud to remember; in this, their position involves active participation in the life of their organization, decision-making; they are less concerned about the future than other professionals who can only anticipate a successful career in the future. With regard to the high level of personal and situational counteractivity in the field of economic affairs, especially those working with external clients ($p \leq 0.01$), we think it is logical that specialists who work with people have a good understanding of their possible reactions, actions and can predict them. Professionals working with external clients have to interact with a large number of new people

every day, making their communication experience more diverse.

It has been found that professionals who work with internal clients are more likely to handle difficult situations through strategic planning and emotional support, and those who work with external clients through proactive and reflective coping ($p \leq 0.01$). We believe that professionals who work with external clients often interact with new people, face conflict situations, work in an ever-changing environment and, if possible, seek to evaluate potential risks and potential problems; and in-house professionals often plan their future and seek help from more experienced and relevant people.

A number of gender differences have been identified: men have higher rates at all three levels of occupational health than women ($p \leq 0.05$), with the exception of health status (except for disease

incidence). It can be assumed that men are more likely to hold senior positions than women and have the time and resources to maintain health; men pay less attention to illnesses and ailments, so the questionnaire shows high self-esteem in terms of occupational health.

Men were found to have a more pronounced temporal orientation of the future and women to have a "transcendent future" ($p \leq 0.05$); women are more likely to be emotionally immersed in events today, while men have a tendency to structure current events and to plan future events ($p \leq 0.05$). In our view, this corresponds to certain facts and gender stereotypes: men are more purposeful and able to structure events that occur, and women are more inclined to religious rituals, more often visit astrologists, horoscopes, look for certain "signs" given by the universe, etc. Men have a more pronounced spatial and temporal ability to smoke than women ($p \leq 0.05$). Men tend to be more strategic in planning, thinking, and preventive coping with than women ($p \leq 0.05$). This may be in line with public opinion: men are considered to be the best strategists who can assess in advance all the risks and take the necessary preventive measures, and women prefer to act situationally.

Analysis of the results of diagnostics of the level of subjective control (according to J. Rotter) showed that the ratio of introversion and extraversion in the respondents approaches a balanced one. This is one of the indicators of an adequate attitude to the problem of occupational health formation and responsibility for its preservation. With regard to personal qualities such as neuroticism and psychosis, they decreased by 42% and 55%, respectively. Self-confidence increased by 1.5-2 times, and in some cases – 3 times. Respondents noted an increase in motivation for forming occupational health, a willingness to activate acquired skills in managing their psycho-emotional and physical state, and professional self-preservation. The implementation of medical practices in health care management has a positive trend in results. Future economic experts become more energetic and enthusiastic, and it will be easier for them to cope with stress and internal stress. The moral climate in the team improves, the

relationships in it; the number of professions is shrinking significantly.

CONCLUSIONS

1. It is determined that the occupational health of specialists of economic sphere depends on their ability to restore disturbed functioning in accordance with the regulation of the volume and type of professional activity; their occupational health combines elements of the psychosocial continuity of the "generations" of professional groups, a comprehensive assessment of their life and work opportunities, especially in the context of fulfilling common tasks; occupational health is defined by motivation for professional activity and in this sense acts as a measure of social well-being. The set of individual-psychological characteristics of the personality and characteristics of the professional environment that affect the occupational health of specialists of economic sphere include: value orientations (high importance of physical and mental health, family life, interesting work and financially secure life), behavioral manifestations (adequate behavior, high level of energy, ambition and involvement in the work, low hostility to others), stress factors of the professional environment (excessive benefits of overcoming strategies (seeking social support, social contact, aggressive actions), and ways to relieve stress (socializing with friends, humorous, relaxing), coping strategies, physical education, etc.).

2. In the perspective of the research we see the definition of characteristics of professionals engaged in other fields of activity, as well as the study of the process of becoming of occupational health at different stages of life of a person (age of maturity, advanced age). In-depth study and the problem of engaging and training psychologists, teachers and managers to participate in the process of formation and preservation of occupational health of the individual in various fields of his activity requires in-depth study. It is necessary to urgently develop social and psychological training and corrective systems that will help to prevent the negative effects associated with the professional destruction of professionals, as well as their occupational health.

Conflict of interests. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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